

REPUBLIC OF CAMEROON

PEACE-WORK-FATHERLAND

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UNIVERSITE DE BUEA

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CEF 401: OPERATIONAL RESEARCH

***USING SIMPLEX METHOD TO SOLVE A LINEAR
PROGRAMMING PROBLEM***

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November 2023

1) ABSTRACT

This document describes a linear programming problem which aims at maximizing profit during the production of two hardware products. It then proposes a solution to this problem. The solution walkthrough is done using the simplex method.

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3)INTRODUCTION

There are many methods to solve the Linear Programming Problem, such as Graphical Method, Trial and Error method, Vector method and Simplex Method.

The graphical method of solving linear programming problems is useful only for problems involving two decision variables and relatively few problem constraints. What happens when we need more decision variables and more problem constraints? We use an algebraic method called the **SIMPLEX METHOD** which was developed by George B. DANTZIG (1914-2005) in 1947 while on assignment with the U.S. Department of the air force.

4)PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

1. Problem Statement

Hardware company develops two hardware products, A and B. Product A requires 10 hours of hardware design, 5 hours of quality assurance, and 1 hour of manufacturing. Product B requires 6 hours of hardware design, 10 hours of quality assurance, and 2 hours of manufacturing. The profit contribution of products A and B are \$23 and \$32 per unit, respectively. In the coming planning period, the company has 2500 hours of hardware design capacity, 2000 hours of quality assurance capacity, and 500 hours of manufacturing capacity. What is the optimal product mix for maximizing profit?

2. Problem Analysis

Operations	Products		Capacity in hours
	A Hrs	B Hrs	
<i>X(Hardware Design)</i>	10	6	2500
<i>Y(Quality Assurance)</i>	5	10	2000
<i>Z(Manufacturing)</i>	1	2	500
<i>Profit per unit</i>	23	32	---

From the above table, we derive the objective function and the constraints

a) Decision Variables:

Let 'a' be the number of units of product A and 'b' be the number of units of product B

b) Objective Function:

$$Z = 23 a + 32 b$$

c) Constraints:

$$10 a + 6 b \leq 2500$$

$$5 a + 10 b \leq 2000$$

$$1 a + 2 b \leq 500$$

$$a \text{ and } b \text{ are } \geq 0.$$

d) Linear Problem:

Maximize	$Z = 23 a + 32 b$
Subject to	
	$10 a + 6 b \leq 2500$
	$5 a + 10 b \leq 2000$
	$1 a + 2 b \leq 500$
	$a, b \geq 0$

5) SOLUTION USING SIMPLEX METHOD

1. Key Words

e) SLACK VARIABLES:

A mathematical representation of surplus resources. In real life problems, it's unlikely that all resources will be used completely, so there usually are unused resources. Slack variables represent the unused resources between the left-hand side and right-hand side of each inequality.

f) BASIC AND NONBASIC VARIABLES:

Basic variables are selected arbitrarily with the restriction that there can be as many basic variables as there are equations. The remaining variables are non-basic variables

g) SIMPLEX TABLEAU:

Most real-world problems are too complex to solve graphically. They have too many corners to evaluate, and the algebraic solutions are lengthy. A simplex tableau is a way to systematically evaluate variable mixes in order to find the best one

h) PIVOT COLUMN, ROW, NUMBER:

- Pivot Column: The column of the tableau representing the variable to be entered into the solution mix.
- Pivot Row: The row of the tableau representing the variable to be replaced in the solution mix.
- Pivot Number: The element in both the pivot column and the pivot row

2. *Solution Roadmap*

a. STEP 1:

The first step of the simplex method requires that each inequality be converted into an equation by including slack variables.

Suppose S_1 hardware design hours, S_2 quality assurance hours and S_3 manufacturing hours remain unused. The constraints become;

$$\begin{aligned}10a + 6b + S_1 + 0S_2 + 0S_3 &= 2500 \\5a + 10b + 0S_1 + S_2 + 0S_3 &= 2000 \\1a + 2b + 0S_1 + 0S_2 + S_3 &= 500\end{aligned}$$

The objective function with zero coefficients;

$$\begin{aligned}Z &= 23a + 32b + 0S_1 + 0S_2 + 0S_3 \\Z - 23a - 32b - 0S_1 - 0S_2 - 0S_3 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

The problem can now be considered as solving a system of 4 linear equations involving the 6 variables (a, b, S_1, S_2, S_3, Z) in such a way that Z has the maximum value;

$$\begin{aligned}Z - 23a - 32b - 0S_1 - 0S_2 - 0S_3 &= 0 \\10a + 6b + S_1 + 0S_2 + 0S_3 &= 2500 \\5a + 10b + 0S_1 + S_2 + 0S_3 &= 2000 \\1a + 2b + 0S_1 + 0S_2 + S_3 &= 500\end{aligned}$$

Now, the system of linear equations can be written in matrix form or as a 4x6 augmented matrix. The initial tableau is;

b. STEP 2:

Basic Variables	a	b	S1	S2	S3	Right Hand Side
Z	-23	-32	0	0	0	0
S1	10	6	1	0	0	2500
S2	5	10	0	1	0	2000
S3	1	2	0	0	1	500

The tableau represents the initial solution;

$a = 0, b = 0, S_1 = 2500, S_2 = 2000, S_3 = 500, Z = 0$
--

The slack variables S1,S2 and S3 form the initial solution mix. The initial solution assumes that all available hours are unused. i.e. The slack variables take the largest possible values. Variables in the solution mix are called **basic variables**. Each basic variable has a column consisting of all 0's except for a single 1. all variables not in the solution mix take the value 0.

In the simplex process, a basic variable in the solution mix is replaced by another variable previously not in the solution mix. The value of the replaced variable is set to 0

c. STEP 3:

Select the pivot column (determine which variable to enter into the solution mix). Choose the column with the “most negative” element in the objective function row.

Basic Variables	a	b	S1	S2	S3	Right Hand Side
Z	-23	-32	0	0	0	0
S1	10	6	1	0	0	2500
S2	5	10	0	1	0	2000
S3	1	2	0	0	1	500

b should enter into the solution mix because each unit of b contributes a profit of \$32 compared with only \$23 for each unit of a

d. STEP 4:

Select the pivot row (determine which variable to replace in the solution mix).

Divide the last element in each row (RHS) by the corresponding element in the pivot column.

The pivot row is the row with the smallest non-negative result excluding 0

S_2 should be replaced by b in the solution mix.

Basic Variables	a	b	S1	S2	S3	Right Hand Side	Ratio
Z	-23	-32	0	0	0	0	$0/-32 = 0$
S1	10	6	1	0	0	2500	$2500/6 = 416.67$
b	5	10	0	1	0	2000	$2000/10 = 200$
S3	1	2	0	0	1	500	$500/2 = 250$

From the above table, we see that the pivot number is 10

e. STEP 5:

Perform elementary row operations to turn the pivot to 1 and turn all the other cells of the key column to 0

To do that, we perform the following elementary row operation one after the other

- $R3 \leftarrow R3/10$
- $R1 \leftarrow R1 + 32 * R3$
- $R2 \leftarrow R2 - 6 * R3$
- $R4 \leftarrow R4 - 2 * R3$

After performing the operations, we get the next tableau as follows

f. **STEP 6:**

Basic Variables	a	b	S1	S2	S3	Right Hand Side
Z	-7	0	0	3.2	0	6400
S1	7	0	1	-0.6	0	1300
b	0.5	1	0	0.1	0	200
S3	0	0	0	-0.2	1	100

The tableau represents the solution;

$a = 0, b = 200, S_1 = 1300, S_2 = 0, S_3 = 100, Z = 6400$
--

The solution proposed by this tableau is not the optimal solution. This is because in the row of the objective function, there is a negative cell at $a=-7$

So to get the optimal solution, we have to do as many iterations as possible until we find the tableau with all positive values at the row of the objective function

To do that, we repeat step 3 till step 6

- STEP 3&4:

Identifying the new pivot row and column, and the pivot number

Basic Variables	a	b	S1	S2	S3	Right Hand Side	Ratio
Z	-7	0	0	3.2	0	6400	$6400/7 = 914.28$
a	7	0	1	-0.6	0	1300	$1300/7 = 185.71$
b	0.5	1	0	0.1	0	200	$200/0.5 = 400$
S3	0	0	0	-0.2	1	100	Undefined

From the above table, we see that the pivot number is 7

- STEP 5&6:
Perform elementary row operations to turn the pivot number to 1 and turn all the other cells of the key column to 0
 - $R2 \leftarrow R2/7$
 - $R1 \leftarrow R1+7*R2$
 - $R3 \leftarrow R3-0.5*R2$
 - $R4 \leftarrow R4$

After performing the operations, we get the next tableau as follows

Basic Variables	a	b	S1	S2	S3	Right Hand Side
Z	0	0	0.98	2.605	0	7699.97
a	1	0	0.14	-0.085	0	185.71
b	0	1	-0.07	0.1425	0	107.145
S3	0	0	0	-0.2	1	100

The tableau represents the solution;

$a = 185.71, b = 107.145, S_1 = 0, S_2 = 0, S_3 = 100, Z = 7700$
--

The solution proposed by this tableau is **the optimal solution**. This is because in the row of the objective function, there is NO negative cell

6) CONCLUSION

Hence the optimal solution to this problem is to manufacture: 185.7 units of A and 107.14 units of B and the optimal return is $Z = \$7,700$

7) REFERENCES

[1]- P. Rama Murthy, Operations Research in; New Age International (P) Ltd., publishers (2007) Second Edition p45